

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

Author: UP Poznan
Creation: 02/25/2025 2:07:00 PM
Sample Name: Proszki

Proszki

Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- Si K

C K_ROI (111)

O K_ROI (32)

Si K_ROI (47)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 9.41 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	97.2	0.00	98.1	16386.3	5.1
O K	2.1	0.01	1.6	512.3	11.0
Si K	0.7	0.01	0.3	158.8	6.1